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THE IMPORTANCE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY PROCEDURES IN THE REHABILITATION OF CHILDREN WITH PNEUMONIA (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Abstract.

The article presents data on the current state of relevant issues in the diagnosis and treatment of pneumonia in children. The authors review various methods of physiotherapy procedures to improve the rehabilitation of patients with pneumonia and evaluate instrumental techniques aimed at improving external respiration functions.

Keywords: *pneumonia, children, physiotherapy procedures, postural drainage, breathing exercises*

Pneumonia is an acute respiratory infectious disease of the respiratory tract characterized by inflammation of the lung parenchyma, infiltration with exudate, and impaired gas exchange. The two most common organisms that cause pneumonia are *Streptococcus pneumoniae* and *Haemophilus influenzae*.

Pneumonia is divided into community-acquired (when infection occurred outside of a hospital setting) and hospital-acquired. Community-acquired pneumonia is common among children worldwide, but morbidity and mortality rates are significantly higher in low-income countries. Hospital-acquired pneumonia and ventilator-associated pneumonia are the second most common hospital-acquired infections. In most cases, children with pneumonia are treated with antibiotics, but in severe cases, hospitalization in an intensive care unit and subsequent oxygen support are required. The accumulation of secretions in the airways due to the infectious process contributes to the worsening of clinical symptoms and leads to increased airway resistance with each breath. The signs and symptoms typical of pneumonia are fever, tachypnea, flaring of the nostrils, cough, shortness of breath, retraction of the lower chest, and decreased blood oxygen saturation [1].

Physiotherapy is an important adjunct in the treatment of most respiratory diseases and is used for children with various respiratory or neuromuscular diseases. The main goal of physiotherapy is to promote the clearance of tracheobronchial secretions, which leads to a decrease in airway resistance, improves gas exchange, and facilitates breathing. However, when performing physiotherapy procedures, it is important to take into account the characteristics of the respiratory system in children. The mechanical principles of physiotherapy methods used for children are similar to those used for adults. Nevertheless, from birth to adulthood, changes occur in the structure and function of breathing, which require constant adaptation when applying physiotherapy methods according to age [1,2].

Physiotherapy procedures are also useful in intensive care units to ensure early disconnection from artificial lung ventilation and to prevent or eliminate respiratory complications.

Children on mechanical ventilation are at risk of oxygen toxicity, atelectasis or lung consolidation, poor mucociliary clearance, and lower functional residual capacity due to inhibition of laryngeal function.

Airway obstruction, infection, and lung atelectasis may occur due to increased secretion volume and viscosity resulting from the use of airways (foreign bodies), poor humidification of ventilator gases, and pathological changes in pneumonia [3].

Chest physiotherapy methods can be classified as traditional and instrumental. Breathing exercises, postural drainage, vibration, and chest compression are traditional methods aimed at promoting mucociliary clearance. Traditional chest physiotherapy can be performed independently or with the help of another person when performing methods that involve manual movement, such as manual vibration, chest compression, and percussion.

Instrumental methods include forced exhalation technique, active cycle breathing technique (ACBT), positive expiratory pressure technique (PEP), and autogenic drainage [1,2].

Breathing exercises are rarely used in neonatal intensive care units because they are difficult for children on mechanical ventilation to perform, but they may be useful for older children who are not on mechanical ventilation [3].

The process of clearing the airways using autogenic drainage is only used in children over eight years of age and is based on active or passive autogenic modulation of airflow and breathing rate based on lung volume.

The chest compression technique involves manually compressing the chest during exhalation and pausing at the end of exhalation to help move pulmonary

secretions, facilitate active inhalation, and improve alveolar ventilation. The rationale for this technique is based on its compressive effect on the airways, increasing the airflow rate.

The forced exhalation technique involves one or two breaths, followed by a period of relaxation and controlled diaphragmatic breathing. The ACBT technique uses cycles of breath control, chest expansion exercises, and forced breathing to remove secretions from the airways. During PEP therapy, positive pressure is created in the airways by exhaling against resistance, allowing air to accumulate distally from obstructive secretions through collateral ventilation channels. PEP therapy can also reduce the duration of fever. The use of autogenic drainage requires patients to breathe using different lung volumes to create optimal airflow in the airways of the lungs in order to enhance the mobilization of secretions from the peripheral to the central airways [4].

The benefits of chest physiotherapy include the evacuation of inflammatory exudates and tracheobronchial secretions, the removal of airway obstruction, the reduction of airway resistance, the improvement of gas exchange, and the reduction of respiratory effort [1,2].

Despite improving the child's respiratory condition and speeding up recovery, in certain situations, physiotherapy can even be harmful, exacerbating bronchospasm, causing pulmonary hypertension, changing the position of foreign bodies, or destabilizing the sick child [1].

Conclusion: Physiotherapy is an important component of comprehensive treatment and recovery from pneumonia. A combination of traditional and instrumental physiotherapy methods will allow achieving optimal rehabilitation results for children with pneumonia.

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